

HO CHI MINH'S IDEOLOGY ABOUT POLITICAL POWER CONTROL AND IT'S MEANING FOR PARTY BUILDING AND RECTIFICATION NOWADAYS

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Abstract: Ho Chi Minh's ideology about political power control is a comprehensive and profound views system on basis points including position, role, importance, purpose and meaning; forces, contents, methods, measures of controlling political power and promoting the role of organizations and offices in the political system as well as people's responsibility in this mission. This article shows basic contents of Ho Chi Minh's ideology about political power control: the importance of controlling political power, organizations and forces, methods and conditions to participate in this task as well as its meaning for Party building and rectification nowadays

Keywords: Control; political power; Ho Chi Minh; meaning; building and rectifying the Party; nowadays.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ho Chi Minh's ideology about political power control is a comprehensive and profound views system on basis points including position, role, importance, purpose and meaning; forces, contents, methods, measures of controlling political power and developing the role of organizations and agencies in the political system as well as people's responsibility in this mission. It is necessary to research and clarify Ho Chi Minh's ideology about political power control because this valid thought is the vital direction, orienting the Communist Party of Vietnam to create and apply it to control the political power in Vietnam, contributing to building and rectifying the Party and making the political system strong and pure.

II. HO CHI MINH'S IDEOLOGY ABOUT POLITICAL POWER CONTROL AND IT'S MEANING FOR PARTY BUILDING AND RECTIFICATION NOWADAYS

A. The basic contents of Ho Chi Minh's ideology about political power control.

Firstly, in terms of the necessity of controlling political power

According to Ho Chi Minh, the importance of controlling political power is reflected via the benefits gained from the control. He specified: "there are three reasons why it is necessary to control: 1. There is such a check to confirm whether staffs are good or not. 2. to be aware of the strong points and weak points of offices. 3. to be aware of strong points and weak points of peremptories and resolutions"¹. Ho Chi Minh considered control as an important step determining effects of work and defects can be caused by poor performance. " nine tenths of defects in our works are driven by lack of control". He affirmed: " proper policies is the root of success... the success or failure of these policies is depend on organizing works, selecting staff and checking steps. If these factors are meager, proper policies shows no value"²

¹. "Hò Chí Minh: *complete works*", National Political Publishing House, Vol 5, page 327,2011.

². "Hò Chí Minh: *complete works*", National Political Publishing House, Vol 5, page 636,2011.

Ho Chi Minh indicated the importance of political power control through warning severe consequences of rotting political power. The most dangerous drawback of it is a collapse of the political regime, given by recession of staff's quality, leading to loss of people's belief. He believed: "a nation, a Party and each person, that is great and inspired does not mean being adulated and adored forever if being hooked on individualism"³.

Ho Chi Minh criticized the abuse of power of several heads of powerful authorities: "people hate presidents and commissioners because they are high-handed. They don't understand Viet Minh's policies so they abuse the power when wielding power, always want to shoot when having some guns and want to attack others when having a sword"⁴. He affirmed drawbacks of "revolutionary officials" are: "being licentious, bureaucratic, despising public opinion, ignoring people due to being high-handed. They forget that they are elected to devote instead of being high-handed"⁵.

Secondly, in terms of organizations and forces participating in controlling political power.

Ho Chi Minh mentioned the role of organizations and forces engaging in controlling political power: 1) the Party "always control staff"; 2) congress: "a pure person doesn't concern the control of anyone, even of congress"; 3) government; 4) "people have right to control to prevent corruption and abuse of power"; 5) staff: "people and staffs control mistakes of leaders";...); 6) Leader: "leaders control staffs' results", etc.

Ho Chi Minh affirmed forces participating controlling political power including: people are a force of political power control; all of political powers come from people and are authorized by them. People do organize political apparatus; officials and Party's members also come from citizens so "people have the right to control and remove representatives who do not deserve people's confidence"⁶. He usually recalled organizations and officials to consult people as well as base on them to build and implement requirements and duties of revolution.

Ho Chi Minh defined objects of political power control: in the relationship between the Party and members, government and cadres, organization and officials. Organizations have an important role and cadres are in charge of organizations that they belong to. In the relationship of organizations, Ho Chi Minh mentioned both subject and object. Central level control local level, superior control inferiority, by contrast, grassroots level control central level, inferiority control superior. Ho Chi Minh defined: "inferiority has to report and superior has to control". In the relationship of individuals, superior control inferiority and inferiority implement controlling the accomplishment process of duties and power of superiors.

Thirdly, in terms of methods and conditions to control political power

Firstly, in terms of methods

Controlling political power from "inside". According to Ho Chi Minh, it is a method of controlling internal political system's organizations. For each cadre/the Party's member/leader, it is self management. For an organization, it is control of a group and individual in this internal organization.

Control by rules, regulations, discipline: charters, rules, regulations of the organization and the national legal system have to be built and updated incessantly. He required: "the law governed by the rule"⁷ and "unhonest people have to be punished by law, even in any position or job"⁸. He directed and directly signed to introduce two Constitutions (1946, 1959), 16 laws, more than 1,300 sub-law documents with 243 decrees, regulations, governing all activities of the State and society.

Control by self criticism and criticism; self control and controlling each other: Ho Chi Minh believed that: "...in the Party, in meetings for discussion, members listen to leaders reporting works, criticize weak points and elect comrades in the executive board. It is a control based on the democratic centralism principle, criticism and self criticism, that the Party has to carry out strictly"⁹. The purpose of self criticism and criticism is assessing personal strong and weak points and of other people in order to boost strong points and eliminate weak points, using strong points to correct the bads, the wrongs. It is

³. "Hồ Chí Minh: *complete works*", National Political Publishing House, Vol 15, page 672,2011.

⁴. "Hồ Chí Minh: *complete works*", National Political Publishing House, Vol 4, page 51,2011.

⁵. "Hồ Chí Minh: *complete works*", National Political Publishing House, Vol 4, page 65,2011.

⁶. "Hồ Chí Minh: *complete works*", National Political Publishing House, Vol 12, page 375,2011.

⁷. "Hồ Chí Minh, *complete works*", National Political Publishing House, vol 1, page 473,2011.

⁸. "Hồ Chí Minh: *complete works*", National Political Publishing House, vol 6, page 127,2011.

⁹. "Hồ Chí Minh: *complete works*", National Political Publishing House, vol 5, page 328,2011.

necessary to have right methods and behaviors to criticize effectively. Self criticism and criticism are implemented regularly, honestly and strictly; “must have comradeship, love each other”, “do not criticize haphazardly and take no responsibility”.

Bottom-up and top-down control: Ho Chi Minh mentioned: “there are two methods of control. First method is bottom-up control, meaning that leaders control cadres’ results. Another one is top-down control, meaning that citizens and cadres supervise leaders’ mistakes and suggest solutions. This is the best way to control staffs”¹⁰. Top-down control has two levels: cadres’ control for leaders and inferiority’s control for superior; citizens’ supervision for leaders. Inferiorities supervise superiors via democratic centralism principle, criticism and self criticism.

Promoting appropriate authorities’ role: Ho Chi Minh believed: “the Party and government have more and more tasks. To perform duties well, Party Committees at all levels have to strengthen supervision, making all Party’s members and officials execute Party’s policies strictly because supervision can promote and educate members and officials to fulfill their duties for the Party and government and set a good example for citizens, then contribute to strengthening the Party’s thought and organizations”¹¹. On inspection work, Ho Chi Minh affirmed: “inspection work is a vital and honorable duty; it monitors and examine the strict execution of the direction, policies, resolutions and directives of the Party and the Government”¹². “To accomplish duties, official’s thinking and behavior should be changed significantly. We have to execute policies of the Party and the government decisively, serve people with utter dedication, and so do the inspection and other sectors”¹³.

Controlling political power from “outside”. According to Ho Chi Minh, controlling power is based on citizens because they grant authority to the state so they have the right to supervise power. He pointed out a bunch of forms, including meet for discussion, criticism, showing opinions and electing boards and councils, etc: “In public, meet for discussion, criticism, showing opinions and electing boards and councils are their way of control over leaders”¹⁴. He affirmed: “Law is belong to people, which is used to prevent harmful activities and protect mutual benefits of most people”¹⁵. He considered it as “a head light”, which helps leadership to be right and prevent high-handed problem of leaders at all levels: supervision can boost the big forces and positive spirit of people, raise awareness of ability and weak points of officials to correct the faults and support timely”¹⁶. According to him: “members speculating in the Party are unmasked thanks to supervision of people and the Party, making the Party become a model and being pure and to serve people with utter dedication. Revolution and all members become the model”¹⁷.

Control by promoting the role of morals. Ho Chi Minh believed that the main reason for depraved political power is revolutionary morals recession and falling into individualism of officials. Therefore, educating revolutionary morals to officials and Party’s members, making them become both leaders and faithful servants of people is the first solution because “public treasure only people having good behaviors and morals. Officials should be exemplary in order direct people”¹⁸.

Secondly, in terms of conditions of political power control.

Conditions of institutions are rules, regulations, law system and organizational structure. Ho Chi Minh required that rules, regulations, and the law system should be specific, clear and appropriate to regulate the organizational structure of offices and organization in the political system. Organizational structure is a political system; inspection boards and inspectors at all levels play an important role.

In terms of forces implementing power control, Ho Chi Minh gave the priority to build a contingent of moral Party’s officials and members, controlling each other, organizations and leaders by giving priority to state benefits. People are coverage, having supreme control jurisdiction over the State and Party’s power. He saw that people are terminative

¹⁰. “Hồ Chí Minh: *complete works*”, National Political Publishing House, vol 5, page 328,2011.

¹¹. “Hồ Chí Minh: *complete works*”, National Political Publishing House, vol 14, page 362,2011.

¹². “Hồ Chí Minh: *complete works*”, National Political Publishing House, vol 13, page 35,2011.

¹³. “Hồ Chí Minh: *complete works*”, National Political Publishing House, vol 13, page 36,2011.

¹⁴. “Hồ Chí Minh: *complete works*”, National Political Publishing House, vol 5, page 328,2011.

¹⁵. “Hồ Chí Minh: *complete works*”, National Political Publishing House, vol 9, page 259,2011.

¹⁶. “Hồ Chí Minh: *complete works*”, National Political Publishing House, vol 5, page 636,2011.

¹⁷. “Hồ Chí Minh: *complete works*”, National Political Publishing House, vol 8, page 60,2011.

¹⁸. “Hồ Chí Minh: *complete works*”, National Political Publishing House, vol 6, page 16, 2011.

conditions to all organizations and activities of Party, the State and revolution, including political power control. It is unavailable to control political power effectively without people.

According to Ho Chi Minh: “there are two factors of effective supervision: firstly, supervision is systemic control and is conducted regularly. Secondly, supervisors are reliable”. Systemic control means that it is organized from central to grassroots levels and has specific and clear projects, plans and processes. “Being conducted regularly” means that it is sustained constantly, preventing temporary movement. Supervisors have to be reliable, moral and have qualities of talent and spirit as well as serve people and the State with utter dedication.

B. It's Meaning for Party Building and Rectification Nowadays.

Ho Chi Minh's ideology is the basic thought and the orientation of Party and Vietnamese people's activities. Points of view for political power control are basic of thought and scientific reasoning elementary for Party's policies and viewpoints in building political system and Party building and rectification; orienting supervision, inspection, prevention of corrupting power and political power control, etc. Via Party's policies and viewpoints, Ho Chi Minh's ideology about political power control has become scientific reasoning elementary, providing orientated elementaries for organizations and individuals of political system in exercising political power. Besides, the ideology system of Ho Chi Minh about political power control has raised public awareness of their role in inspection, urging the public to supervise activities of Party, the State and officials consciously and effectively. Nowadays, recession in political thought and morals and corrupting power are burning in a large part of officials, having severe impacts. During the arduous period of fighting against these problems, Ho Chi Minh's ideology showed its great value in Party building and rectification and establishing a pure, strong and effective political system.

In a period of operating in secret, Communist Party of Vietnam raised a viewpoint of power belonging to the public under the Party's direction. “Chánh cương vắn tắt” written by Ho Chi Minh indicated: the duty of Vietnamese revolution is to throw off the yoke of French colonialism and feudal regime, making Vietnam independent, build the government of workers, peasants and soldiers and held the army force that workers, peasants engaging in. So, the Vietnamese Party defined that enforcement mechanism includes Party leading and the State representing the public to control the nation.

The platform of developing country in the transitional period to socialism (1991) added that Vietnamese political policy is building a socialist country belonging to the people and for the people, which is based on an alliance between the working class, the peasantry, and the intelligentsia and driven by the Party; fully exercising the democratic rights of citizens, keep social rules strictly and exercising dictatorship over activities violating benefits of the State and the people. This platform outlined the essence of the mechanism for exercising power to manage society in Vietnam as the Party leading, the State of the people, by the people, for the people exercising the rights to manage society and dictatorship over the enemy and provided a policy of building socialist country in the behalf of a tool in fulfilling the people's mastery and protecting benefits of most citizens. To control the power, it is necessary to build a pure Party, exercise the principle of democratic centralism, have a strong attachment to the people and emphasize that state power is unified, with the close coordination of state agencies in the exercise of three rights: legislative, executive and judicial. At the congress, the Party warned to prevent the risk of mistakes in policies, bureaucracy and the degeneracy of cadres and Party members.

Moreover, the ninth National Congress of the Party concretized the Party's leadership method on the State and society: leadership through setting policies, guidelines and major policies orienting the developing and inspecting the organization and implementation of the Party's policies and Constitution as well as national laws. To exercise power effectively in accordance with the market economy, we advocate: strengthen Party's organizational system and renew organization, machinery of state offices and sociopolitical organizations.

Tenth National Party Congress defined: “Building mechanism of a socialist law-governed State, ensuring principle that all State powers belong to the people; state power is unified, with the close coordination of state agencies in the exercise of the legislative, executive and judicial”. The Congress also set requirements for the Party to self-innovate and self-correct; strengthen the building of a pure and strong Party in terms of politics, ideology and organization; promote raising awareness, practice moral qualities, fight against degeneracy and corruption; renovate and strengthen the Party's organizational system and political system, improve the quality of cadres and party members; comprehensive renew of staff work; promote the inspection and supervision; innovate leadership methods and working styles; closely stick to the people and base on the people to build the Party. In particular, it is important to prevent the risk of mistakes in direction, degeneracy, bureaucracy, and isolation from the people.

The platform of developing country in the transitional period to socialism (supplemented and developed in 2011) affirmed: "state power is unified, with the close coordination of state agencies in the exercise of legislative, executive and judicial" . At the 11th National Party Congress, the view of controlling state power was given more drastically. The Congress had prepared conditions for the Party to monitor the State's management activities more effectively. As a result of these efforts, the Central Steering Committee for Anti-corruption under the Government, was changed to under the Politburo, led by the General Secretary and re-established the Committee for Internal Affairs to help The Party inspects and supervises cadres and party members holding the power.

The document of the 12th National Congress of the Party specified: "Continue to promote socialist democracy, ensuring that all state power belongs to the people. All policies and guidelines of the Party and policies and laws of the State derive from the people's aspirations, rights and advantages and are consulted by the people. Democracy must be fully and seriously implemented in all sectors of social life, ensuring the participation of the people at all stages of the decision-making process related to their benefits and lives" . And, it is necessary to "complete and strictly implement the power control mechanism, prevention of abuse of power, violation of disciplines and rules" . So, Party's confirm again that state power belongs to the people not only is an affirmation of a principle but also emphasizes the requirement of establishing a mechanism to exercise the people's power of inspection and supervision.

In the fact of lacking fairness in the exercise of power, the Resolution of the 4th Plenum and Regulation No. 205-QD/TW of the 12th Politburo emphasized discipline tightened in the Party, implementing democracy exactly and closely inspection and supervision; strictly dealing with mistakes of leaders and cadres; requiring each leaders and managerial cadre to constantly improve, train, manage and control themselves over the power ambitions and the temptation of material interests in the internal degeneration, "self-evolution" and "self-transformation".

The 13th National Party Congress proposed purposes including raising ability in leadership and holding power and boosting Party's power; building a pure and strong Party; strengthening the people's belief in Party, State and socialism regim,... The Party emphasized: it is necessary to define clearly the roles, positions, functions, tasks and powers of state agencies in the exercise of legislative, executive and judicial powers on the basis of the rule of jurisdiction, ensure that State power is unified, having a clear assignment, closely coordination and promoting the control over the state power" . This confirm shows the correct awareness and applying of the Party in the new conditions of political power control, especially state power to protect supreme rights and benefits of the people as well as build a socialist law-governed State of the people, by the people and for the people based on the motto "people know, people discuss, people do, people supervise and people benefit".

III. CONCLUSION

Ho Chi Minh's ideology about political power control is a basic of thought and scientific reasoning elementary for Party's policies and viewpoints in building political systems and Party building and rectification; orienting supervision, inspection, prevention of corrupting power and political power control,etc. Via Party's policies and viewpoints, Ho Chi Minh's ideology about political power control has become scientific reasoning elementary, providing orientated elementaries for organizations and individuals of political system in exercising political power. During the arduous period of fighting against recession in political thought and corrupting power, Ho Chi Minh's ideology shows its great value in Party building and rectification and establishing a pure, strong and effective political system.

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